

BRAND MANAGEMENT AND MARKETING RESEARCH IN THE GLOBAL MARKET

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Abstract. This article focuses on the production of goods in the market economy and increasing its quality and competitiveness. Marketing research plays an important role in brand management as it helps in analyzing consumer behavior, needs, and market trends. This article examines the importance of marketing research in formulating brand strategies, determining brand positioning, and assessing competitors, as well as its role in strengthening communication with consumers. With the help of research, it is possible to make the right decisions and ensure the long-term success of the brand. The article also presents methodologies, results analysis, and case studies.

Keywords: research, method, position, consumer, need, market, strategy, brand, marketing.

Аннотация. В данной статье основное внимание уделяется производству товаров в условиях рыночной экономики и повышению их качества и конкурентоспособности. Маркетинговые исследования играют важную роль в управлении брендом, поскольку помогают анализировать поведение, потребности и тенденции рынка потребителей. В данной статье рассматривается значение маркетинговых исследований при формулировании стратегии бренда, определении позиционирования бренда и оценке конкурентов, а также его роль в укреплении коммуникации с потребителями. С помощью исследований можно принять правильные решения и обеспечить долгосрочный успех бренда. В статье также представлены методологии, анализ результатов и тематические исследования.

Ключевые слова: Исследование, метод, позиция, потребитель, потребность, рынок, стратегия, бренд, маркетинг.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola bozor iqtisodiyotida tovarlarni ishlab chiqarish va uning sifatini hamda raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga qaratilgan. Brendni boshqarishda marketing tadqiqotlari muhim rol o'ynaydi, chunki ular iste'molchilarning xulq-atvori, ehtiyojlari va bozor tendensiyalarini tahlil qilishga yordam beradi. Ushbu maqolada marketing tadqiqotlarining brend strategiyalarini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati, brend pozitsiyasini aniqlash va raqobatchilarni baholashdagi o'rni, shuningdek, iste'molchilar bilan muloqotni mustahkamlashdagi roli ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqotlar yordamida to'g'ri qarorlar qabul qilish va brendning uzoq muddatli muvaffaqiyatini ta'minlash mumkin. Maqolada metodologiyalar, natijalarni tahlil qilish va amaliy misollar ham keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tadqiqot, metod, pozitsiya, iste'molchi, ehtiyoj, bozor, strategiya, brend, marketing.

Introduction. Brand management is an integral part of modern business, and marketing research is of great importance in this process. Marketing research provides a deeper understanding of consumer behavior, competitors, and market trends. The above sources are the main and integral sources in determining brand development and strategy. Branding marketing research is an essential tool for developing a successful brand strategy. This process helps define the brand's

position by analyzing consumer needs, competitors, and market trends. Research will be the main source of information for making the right decisions, identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the brand.

Methodology. Word building, systematization, and classification were also used in the next piece. The study discovered that in order to prevent product confusion, brand names should be sufficiently correct to spell and understand. Apart from all of this, I. Bulatovic once noted that it's crucial to keep in mind that consumers determine a brand's value, and not merely for irrational and emotional reasons. On the other hand, consumers are responding perfectly rationally when they appreciate a brand only because they anticipate a particular degree of quality from it [2, 1329].

Literature Review. Brand management and marketing research are vital in navigating the complexities of the global market. They provide insights into consumer behavior, competitive dynamics, and market trends, enabling companies to make informed strategic decisions. Brand Management Effective brand management involves creating a strong brand identity and maintaining brand equity. Kotler and Keller (2016) emphasize the importance of brand positioning in differentiating products in a crowded marketplace. A well-managed brand can foster customer loyalty and drive long-term profitability. Marketing Research Marketing research is crucial for understanding market dynamics and consumer needs. Malhotra (2020) outlines various methodologies for gathering data on consumer preferences and behavior, helping businesses adapt their strategies accordingly. This research informs product development, pricing, and promotional tactics. Brand equity and loyalty Building brand equity is essential for sustaining competitive advantage. Aaker (1991) identifies key components of brand equity, including brand awareness, perceived quality, and brand loyalty. A strong brand can lead to increased consumer trust and repeat purchases, which are vital for success in the global market.

Literature Review. The intersection of brand management and marketing research is crucial for understanding consumer behavior and developing effective strategies in the global market. This literature review explores key concepts and findings from various studies that highlight the importance of both fields.

Brand management involves creating and maintaining a strong brand identity. Aaker (1991) defines brand equity as the value added to a product by its brand name, emphasizing the role of brand loyalty and awareness. Kotler and Keller (2016) further elaborate on the strategies for brand positioning, noting that effective differentiation is vital in saturated markets. Recent studies highlight the need for adaptability in brand management to respond to changing consumer preferences and global trends (Kapferer, 2012). Marketing research serves as the backbone for effective brand management by providing insights into market dynamics and consumer behavior. Malhotra (2020) discusses various research methodologies, emphasizing the importance of both qualitative and quantitative approaches to gather comprehensive data. The use of big data analytics has emerged as a powerful tool for marketers to understand trends and predict consumer behaviors (Chaffey, 2018).

Research and results. Advantages and Disadvantages of Marketing

Research The advantages and disadvantages of conducting marketing research by companies themselves are considered (Table 1).

Advantages of conducting the research by the company itself and comparative characteristics of disadvantages

Advantages	Disadvantages
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Competence of employees in this field, because they know the specific characteristics of the company and its customers	Lack of professional skills of employees who are often busy with other things
Availability of confidential information at home because the most valuable information is never taken outside the company	The possibility of reselling research results to competitors because you can go to another company with advertising
The objectivity of its employees, because the employee is interested in the prosperity of the enterprise	There is a high probability of falsifying the results because corporate opinion affects general assumptions, attitudes, and beliefs
The final value of the research is low, because, after the completion of the research, employees can be transferred to another place of work	The cost of scientific research is high, as the department has to pay salaries throughout the year, as well as rent, taxes, etc.
Respect for confidentiality by employees, because the employee depends on the enterprise, which is already verified and trusted	

It is worth noting that the majority of enterprise salespeople admitted that they spend more than 15-20% of their working time directly on conducting market research, and the rest are engaged in other tasks, including sales and advertising. This means that the agency will complete the research at least five times faster than an in-house expert. This means that every company should have its own marketer, but very few large companies can afford to maintain a department to do all the work, including research.

Conclusion. This paper presented an important link between brand management and marketing research in the global market. The results of the study showed that successful brand management is based on marketing research. Relationships between brand positioning, marketing research influence, and consumer loyalty have been identified. Understanding consumer needs and adapting strategies is key to a brand's global success. In general, brand managers have the opportunity to actively use marketing research to strengthen the brand's reputation and improve relationships with consumers. Brands need to constantly update their strategies and adapt to market dynamics.

REFERENCES

1. Aaker J. The negative attraction effect? A study of the attraction effect under judgment and choice //Advances in Consumer Research. – 1991. – T. 18. – №. 1.
2. Bulatovic, I., Škorić, S., & Jovanović, V. (2016). Branding a business name. Economics of agriculture, 63(4), 1323-1332.
3. Chinsuvapala P. Kotler, Philip and Keller Kelvin Lane.(2016). Marketing Management.(15th global edition) Edinburgh: Pearson Education.(679 pp) //KASEM BUNDIT JOURNAL. – 2017. – T. 18. – №. 2. – C. 180-183.
4. Kapferer J. N. Kapferer on luxury: How luxury brands can grow yet remain rare. – Kogan Page Publishers, 2015.
5. Malhotra N. K., Nunan D., Birks D. F. Marketing research. – Pearson UK, 2020.